

A Narrative Review On Social Enterprises To Tackle Cyber-Bullying And Cyber Crimes

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Abstract : Cybercrime has become a global issue, affecting individuals, businesses, and governments worldwide. As the reliance on digital technology continues to grow, cybercriminals have found novel methods to take advantage of weaknesses and perpetrate illegal activities online. The main reasons which contribute to this sharp rise in the cases of cyberbullying are the widespread availability of the internet, the anonymity provided by the sites and the urge to exert power. Victims generally face severe consequences like deteriorating mental health, depression and suicidal tendency. The bullies also show a correlation with substance abuse, dysfunctional families and mental health struggles. Introduction of intervention programs in schools and educational centres along with social apps which are now available online, the mitigation measures for cyberbullying have increased exponentially. This article explores the effect of cyberbullying on the victims, the offenders and the bystanders. It evaluates the possible reasons a cyberbully chooses to attempt the practice and what role a bystander has during the occurrence of the bullying. Following that social start-ups and policies combating cyberbullying are listed. The impact created by these intervention programs and social policies is discussed. Overall, the advent of cybercrime has transformed the landscape of crime and security, presenting new challenges and opportunities for countries around the world.

IndexTerms - cyber victimisation, Cyberbullying, Intervention programs, Social enterprise, Bystanders

1. INTRODUCTION

Youngsters move in a zone on the internet where typical barriers in real life appear to vanish and peer connections are made more easily. Young people's lives are made easier by technology, but there are risks associated with its use. One of these risks is cyberbullying, which is one of the issues that communication technologies can cause. Cyberbullying is an abusive behaviour that involves using internet communication and is committed by one or more people addressed to another person or group of people who are unable to protect themselves (Carter, 2013). It is driven by factors such as contact without physical contact, apparent anonymity, and simple access to electronic communication (Gini et al., 2007). In the absence of well-defined rules for conducting oneself professionally on social media or other electronic platforms, coupled with minimal accountability for users, an increasing reliance on electronic communication, and a lack of monitoring, there is a greater likelihood of encountering derogatory remarks, harassment, and disruptions (Kibbe & Chhaya, 2022). The goal is to humiliate, insult, hurt, embarrass, get even, have fun, and/or assert dominance over people. It includes several modes (such as flame, denigration, and defamation, utilising obscene symbols, sexual harassment, exclusion, harassment, and slandering) and subcategories (such as texting, email, and social media).

A study looked at the connection between psychological problems and the prevalence of cyberbullying among elementary school children. The findings showed a moderately favourable connection between psychoticism and the amount of exposure to virtual bullying (Ayas & Deniz, 2014). Various psychological symptoms have been linked to exposure to cyberbullying, social anxiety, psychoticism, hostility, low self-esteem, stress, anxiety, loneliness, despair, emotions, and suicide in several studies (Juvonen & Gross, 2008; Arıca, 2009; Raskauskas & Stoltz, 2007; Erdur-Baker & Tanrikulu, 2010; Cetin et al., 2011; Katzer et al., 2009; Hinduja & Patchin, 2009a,b; Leishman, 2002; Brean, 2005; Sharif, 2008). In a study done by over 1,395 students in Finland, about 16.8% of the respondents reported being cyberbullied. The study also showed that girls were more prone to cyberbullying than boys and it was often a continuation of traditional bullying (Juvonen & Gross, 2008). Cultural differences can either encourage or discourage cyberbullying depending on social responses, cultural norms, and protection difficulties. The intervention measures started by social enterprises that were implemented in Australia are a prime illustration of the significance of the macro system. This country has implemented interventions in educational facilities, working with students, instructors, and families for decades (Lozano-Blasco et al.). In this review paper, we defined the effects of cyberbullying on its three stakeholders: the victim, the perpetrator and the bystanders. We have also discussed various social start-ups and governmental organisations tackling cyberbullying. In the end, we have discussed the preventive measures of cyberbullying and looked at the future research prospects in combating cyberbullying

2. Stakeholders of cyberbullying

2.1 The victim

The mental and emotional well-being of the victim, as well as their physical health, can be substantially affected by cyberbullying. A consistent link has been established between the victim and low self-esteem (Patchin & Hinduja, 2010), anxiety (Kowalski & Limber, 2013), depression (Kowalski & Limber, 2013; Li, 2005) and social withdrawal which can stem into suicidal thoughts (Hinduja & Patchin, 2010). Cyberbullying is also known to impact a victim's academic performance as they may have difficulty concentrating and completing school work (Mishna et al., 2012; Kowalski & Limber, 2013; Bonanno & Hymel, 2013). According to a study, 10 to 15-year-olds who encountered online harassment were found to have an elevated propensity for alcohol and drug use, as well as an increased tendency towards behaviour problems and bringing weapons to school (Ybarra et al., 2007). The victims of cyberbullying often miss school as well (Hinduja & Patchin, 2010). The victims also suffer from a number of physical symptoms because of cyberbullying which can include headaches, stomach aches and trouble sleeping. A study claimed to have explored the association between cyberbullying victimisation and psychosocial distress, as well as the obstacles to leading a healthy lifestyle, among severely overweight youngsters (DeSmet et al., 2014).

It was noted that individuals who were targets of traditional bullying also experienced victimisation through electronic or cyber means (Raskauskas & Stoltz, 2007b). Unlike traditional bullying studies where males are more frequently involved as bully-victims, females were found to be more likely than males to be bully victims in this case (Mishna et al., 2012). Victimisation was higher among nonheterosexual identified youths (Schneider et al., 2012). The likelihood of cyberbullying increases among adolescents from racial and ethnic groups who are perceived to be immigrants, hold certain religious beliefs or are portrayed negatively by the majority population (Albdour et al., 2019). This study examines how online racial discrimination affects the psychological well-being of adolescents, with a focus on the differences in experiences between African American and Latino youth and their white counterparts. The results indicate that African American and Latino adolescents report higher levels of online racial discrimination than white adolescents (Tynes et al., 2008). Undoubtedly the victim suffers a great amount of physical, psychological, social and mental distress which may lead to severe consequences if not monitored.

2.2 The offender

Developing effective prevention and intervention strategies to combat cyberbullying requires a thorough understanding of the role played by the cyberbully. While extensive investigation has been conducted on the repercussions of cyberbullying on victims and preventive measures, there is limited information available on the effects on the bullies themselves (Smokowski & Evans, 2019). A study discovered that the most significant factor contributing to someone becoming a cyberbully was previous exposure to cyber victimisation (Quintana-Orts & Rey, 2018). Other authors support this notion and have noted that minors involved in cyberbullying experience more family conflicts, less cohesiveness, poor communication skills, and engage in disrespectful communication with their parents at a much higher rate than their counterparts. As a result, these authors concluded that these adolescents have unstable household (Buelga et al., 2017). Another study found that the level of parental control is a moderating variable that can decrease the likelihood of a child becoming a cyberbully (Hood & Duffy, 2018). According to a correction to an article titled "Bullying in the Digital Age: A Critical Review and Meta-Analysis of Cyberbullying Research among Youth", families play a crucial role in safeguarding against inappropriate use and introduction of new technologies. Additionally, this author suggested that increased use of the internet is associated with an increased likelihood of engaging in cyberbullying. (Kowalski et al., 2014). The following study surveyed a sample of Australian adolescents who reported engaging in cyberbullying behaviour and found that while cyberbullies were aware of the harm they caused to their victims, they tended to downplay the severity of their actions and minimise the impact on their victims' mental health. Simultaneously, individuals who engage in cyberbullying have also reported experiencing adverse psychological outcomes, such as feelings of anxiety, depression, and social isolation (Campbell et al., 2013). A previous study reported that 39% of students who engaged in online harassment dropped out of school, 37% exhibited delinquent behaviour, 32% engaged in frequent substance abuse, and 16% experienced severe depression (Ybarra & Mitchell, 2004).

2.3 The bystanders

Individuals who witness cyberbullying as it occurs and does not intervene are known as bystanders, and they play a critical role in the bullying process (Machackova, 2020; Pepler et al., 2021). There may be many bystanders present at once in the online environment because of its capacity for anonymity (Brody & Vangelisti, 2015). These bystanders' retaliatory actions are vital to the persistence of cyberbullying occurrences and whatever negative effects they may have on the victim and perpetrator. Bystanders' response actions can be either hostile (e.g., threatening the bully), or constructively bully- or victim-focused (e.g., encouraging the perpetrator to cease their actions or providing the target with emotional assistance) (Macaulay et al., 2022).

A study which included a sample of 1979 teenagers in grades 7 through 9, was spread over 16 schools and 158 classrooms. Analysis was carried out in MLwiN 2.32. The findings of the studies supported the multifaceted nature of bystander behaviour and behavioural intention. The two strongest personal indicators of constructive bystander conduct were friendship with the victim and positive intentions. Positive outcome expectations of the bystanders' activities for the victim were the strongest predictors of their intention to behave well. Intentions for bad behaviour and moral disengagement attitudes were the best predictors of negative bystander behaviour (DeSmet et al., 2016). Another study claimed that helping behaviour was related to high levels of confidence and self-esteem, but passively observing conduct was connected with low levels of confidence and self-esteem. When bystanders see cyberbullying happening, they might not know how to react or have the necessary abilities (Gini et al., 2007).

3. Start-ups/Enterprises which are working to solve this problem

It is evident that there is a need for intervention and support programs to combat cyberbullying among adolescents and adults. Schools in Europe, America and Canada have already started to implement such programs and many social enterprises are coming up with websites and apps providing resources to deal with this adverse situation (Tavalaei & Cennamo, 2021).

3.1 Apps to stop cyberbullying:

3.1.1 Belly Button:

The Bully Button program provides a practical solution for users to easily report and flag instances of online harassment. This program is frequently used by schools to complement their in-person anti-bullying efforts (Wyman, 2022). By removing the "bystander effect," which occurs when children see bullying but feel obligated to remain silent because everyone else is, Bully Button aids schools in combating bullying. Bully Button includes preset report templates to simplify the reporting process and encourage students to reflect on instances of online harassment (goodlifefamilyadmin, 2021).

3.1.2 ReThink – Stop Cyberbullying:

ReThink is a well-known anti-cyberbullying app that is praised for being a cutting-edge and non-intrusive solution to address the issue of cyberbullying. The app was created by a teenage girl who was personally affected by a report she read about cyber bullying (ReThink, n.d.). ReThink's goal is to stop incidents of cyberbullying before they even happen. The software notifies users when a message contains content that has been predetermined to be abusive or nasty and gives them the option to edit or reconsider their comments. The user then needs to change their word choice. This additional push to consider word choice might help stop cyberbullies from injuring other people (Vikky, 2022).

3.1.3 Take a Stand Together:

Take a Stand Together is an app created by the Australian educational authority to combat cyberbullying among schoolchildren. This application offers users a range of resources and tools to address cyberbullying, including practical advice and emotional support for those who have experienced harassment. (Sturman, n.d.). The application provides young people with stories, advice, and cartoon videos that describe the various forms of bullying. (Take a Stand Together - This App Trains Kids to Face and Overcome Bullying at School — Steemit, 2019).

4.2 Social startups tackling cyberbullying:

4.2.1 Bodyguard:

Bodyguard is a French firm that provides a smartphone application to shield people and organisations from online bullying. The system functions as a real-time moderator by understanding text, spotting offensive comments even when emojis, abbreviations, restricted words, and typos are used. In order to prevent the impacted user from reading these remarks, the solution then deletes them (*Bodyguard*, n.d.). Users can change the level of protection from insults, threats, trolling, body-shaming, racism, homophobia, misogyny, hate, and sexual or moral harassment using this feature. The software also alerts parents via email if their children post harsh comments or get comments from bullies. Businesses can use the solution to monitor their web platforms (Dillet, 2021).

4.2.2 Kaitiaki:

Kaitiaki is an Italian start-up that offers the products Kaitiaki SAFE and Kaitiaki EDU to help parents and schools to protect kids from cyberbullying. Kaitiaki SAFE can analyse photographs and videos, identify nudity and offensive language, comprehend text, and identify unsafe behaviour patterns and profile anomalies (*Kaitiaki*, 2020). Additionally, when it finds threats, the software notifies the parents or profile managers. It also picks up new behavioural patterns, which helps it solve new problems. With the aid of Kaitiaki EDU, schools may assess their potential exposure to cyberbullying and teach kids to identify the contexts and terminologies of such incidents (*Kaitiaki*, 2020).

4.2.3 Someturva:

A Finnish business called Someturva creates software that enables influencers to submit anonymous reports of instances of online sexual harassment (*The Hub*, n.d.). The solution then designates a specialist attorney and social psychologist to review the case. The user is then given tools to handle the situation and a personal assessment. They can discuss their situation and receive solution suggestions via a virtual meeting, thanks to the program (Insights, 2021).

4.3 Government organisations against Cyberbullying

4.3.1 National Counseling Society-UK

They are crucial to the UK counselling industry, and in May 2013, the Society became one of the first organizations to be granted accredited register status under the PSA's accredited register program. The relationship between the counsellor and client is crucial for the success of therapy, according to their beliefs, and counselling (and associated therapies) should be viewed as a vocation (not simply a job but a worthy employment). They encourage and support counselling as well as counsellors, and give a wide range of advantages to our members and training providers. To assist healthcare professionals and individuals who work with the public, they have also developed and published online CPD courses (Society, 2019).

4.3.2 National Counseling Society-Anti-Bullying Alliance

It was established by the Anti-Bullying Alliance with the goal of combating and ending bullying. This year's theme is "Reach Out," which encourages individuals to take action to lessen the harm and suffering that bullying causes. Over 200 organizations have joined together to form the Anti-Bullying Alliance to combat bullying. They have their headquarters at the National Children's Bureau, a children's charity. They adore seeing so many young people engaging in anti-bullying initiatives, whether it's wearing odd socks on Odd Sock Day, participating in anti-bullying events at your school or institution, or even planning your own anti-bullying event, fundraiser, or activity (*Anti-Bullying Alliance*, n.d.).

4.3.3 Stopbullying

Anti-bullying initiatives have gained significant attention in recent years, both online and offline. One such initiative is Stopbullying.gov, which was revitalized in 2012. The website, which is managed by the United States Department of Health & Human Services in collaboration with the Departments of Education and Justice, provides a plethora of educational and informative resources to help prevent and combat bullying, including cyberbullying. The resources are geared towards parents, educators, children, teenagers, and the community. All materials on the website are open to public access and can be freely copied, distributed, or transmitted (D'Auria, 2014).

5. Prevention of cyberbullying

Fig 1: How to be safe online? (10 Best Ways to Prevent Cyberbullying Online, n.d.)

Nobody ought to experience cyberbullying. Children and teenagers who experience it feel scared, upset, and confused. They frequently don't understand why they are being attacked, and they frequently don't know how to find support in this difficult and often frightening circumstance. To stop, curtail, or eradicate cyberbullying, both the home and the school must work together (Feinberg & Roby, n.d.). A study which focused on high school students giving advice to younger pupils to counteract cyberbullying mentioned the need to use lectures, organised games or theatre to approach the subject to increase the awareness against cyberbullying. They also believed that younger pupils need to learn the "netiquette", the cautious approach to social media (Berne et al., 2019). The importance of having a school psychologist in tackling such a crisis is immeasurable. School psychologists can play a crucial role in evaluating the frequency and seriousness of cyberbullying among students. They can also provide counselling and support to students who have been bullied, as well as those who have engaged in cyberbullying. Finally, they can be useful in creating prevention programmes intended to deal with the issue of cyberbullying among adolescents in school (Diamanduros et al., 2008). Parents also need to monitor the internet use for middle school pupils and introduce the young age adults to preventive strategies and resources (Völlink et al., 2015).

Social media sites are also taking preventive steps to decrease the indulgence of youth in cyberbullying. The Facebook Bullying Prevention Hub is currently accessible to support and assist Teenagers, Parents, and Educators. Twitter has recently launched a new feature called "Twitter's Safety Mode," which uses AI technology to automatically detect and limit the reach of potentially harmful tweets, as well as prevent accounts that frequently break Twitter's rules from interacting with other users. This feature is designed to reduce the impact of online abuse and harassment on Twitter. Additionally, there are several tools and software programs available to help users block and report abusive behaviour on social media platforms. Most of the social media platforms today have policies that prohibit the use of offensive and derogatory language (Perera & Fernando, 2021). Even with the presence of ample resources to stop cyber victimisation in school, online and at home, combating cyberbullying is a long term process and would require constant efforts to keep our adolescents safe from a technology known to spread.

6. Impact created by the social start-ups and intervention programs

The programs and the sessions devised by the social start-ups which are actively involved in combating cyberbullying have been fruitful in bringing about a change. KiVa antibullying program, a school based intervention program is designed to stop cyber and traditional bullying in elementary schools effectively reducing both bullying perpetration and victimisation, and in improving students' psychological well-being. The effects were strongest for students who had initially reported high levels of bullying involvement or who were identified as high-risk for future involvement in bullying (Kärnä et al., 2011). A study analysed the effectiveness of TABBY (Threat Assessment of Bullying Behaviour in Youth), a preventive program funded by Europe and implemented in schools. The program involved 401 elementary school students. The students who received the program reported significantly fewer cyberbullying behaviours compared to the control group (Touloupis & Athanasiades, 2022). This study underscored the importance of social support in mitigating the negative effects of bullying and victimisation, and suggests that interventions aimed at increasing social support may be effective in reducing psychopathic tendencies in adolescents (Despoti et al., 2020). A systematic review of 31 studies which included education programs, cognitive-behavioural therapy, social and mental well-being programs concluded that cyberbullying interventions can be effective in reducing cyberbullying behaviour and improving outcomes for youth and parents (Hutson et al., 2017). With the backing of their administrations, educational communities are striving to eliminate cyberbullying through innovative educational projects, which has become a significant challenge (Lozano-Blasco et al., 2020). Current preventive strategies for teaching e-safety in schools primarily focus on imparting information, rather than encouraging active participation from children. Interactive web-based learning platforms like "BE SMART WHEN ONLINE" utilise multimedia to actively engage children in learning about e-safety, including topics such as personal data protection, cyberbullying prevention, and hacker protection. The platform provides interactive quizzes and games with immediate feedback to help children improve their skills, as well as discussion forums where they can reflect on their learning by posting comments (Nicolaidou & Venizelou, 2016).

According to a recent meta-analysis, Australia has a 7.02% victimisation rate for cyberbullying and a 3.45% perpetrator rate. This study provides a thorough summary of this phenomena in Australia and studies from 1990 to 2015. Traditional bullying has declined, and they hypothesise that public awareness initiatives may have played a role in this decline. They suggested that putting anti-bullying measures in place is a successful strategy for preventing mental illness (Jadambaa et al., 2019). According to some authors, it is important to monitor adolescent internet use (Baldry et al., 2015). Other authors also emphasise the significant role of the family, which has been incorporated in anti-bullying intervention programs (Beringer, 2011; Cross & Barnes, 2014). A systematic review was conducted which evaluated the effectiveness of three Australian intervention models, including "Friendly schools" (Cross et al., 2011), "Creating a Peaceful School Learning Environment" (CAPSLE) (Fonagy et al., 2009), and "CBT" (Berry & Hunt, 2009). The interventions mentioned in the study included participation from both the affected individuals and their families. These interventions had different levels of effectiveness, with CAPSLE having a high efficacy, especially for victims, and the Cyber Friendly Schools (CFS) method reducing both cyberbullying victimization and perpetration rates. However, the authors suggested that future research should incorporate the role of families in these interventions (Cantone et al., 2015). Inclusion of cyberbullying prevention programs which have been developed in the form of social enterprises have proven their need and importance in dealing with

6. Conclusion

Cyberbullying is a widespread problem that can have severe negative impacts on its victims, regardless of their age, race, gender, or socioeconomic status. While there is no single solution to this complex problem, cyberbullying startups have emerged as an important force in the fight against online harassment. By providing innovative and effective tools and services, these startups empower individuals, schools, and organisations to prevent, address, and mitigate the impact of cyberbullying. A considerable progress has been made in stopping cyberbullying in online spaces by the introduction of intervention programs and prevention strategies but a lot is yet to be done. Adolescents need to understand when they are being cyberbullied and they should be well aware of the steps they need to take to get out of this situation. Parents need to create a healthy and approachable environment in home for the children to approach them with their problems which may include cyberbullying. Intervention programs and school psychologists are now a part of curriculum in many American and European schools but somehow they are still a luxury in Asian and African countries. Talking about the research aspect, the American and European schools have been analysed thoroughly for the penetration and effect of cyberbullying but the Asian and African countries haven't yet thoroughly analysed. Meta Analysis of cyberbullying in developing countries needs to be compared to developed countries to check the special requirements and factors which were missed in previous studies. The importance of cyberbullying startups and specially designed intervention programs cannot be overstated. Their work is critical in ensuring that our online spaces are safe and inclusive for all. Through their research, advocacy, and technological advancements, these startups are creating a world in which online harassment is not tolerated, and victims are supported and protected. They might be required to increase their reach to other parts of the world as well. The sustained support and investment in these startups are crucial to ensure that they have the necessary resources and capability to create a long-lasting effect on this critical issue.

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